

Guidance for TU/e Supervisors for PhDs

Key things to check and discuss when reviewing Data Management Plans (DMP)

<i>Project title</i>	
<i>Name of PhD candidate</i>	
<i>Name of Supervisor/s</i>	
<i>Date of review</i>	

Instructions: Use this checklist to guide your discussion of the PhD candidate's (DMP) during the 9-month evaluation or at any other relevant moment in the research process.

- **Read the DMP** before the meeting.
- **Discuss each point** with the candidate and tick items once addressed.
- **Note concerns or required actions** in the “Remarks” column.
- **List agreed next steps** in the “Plan of action” section (e.g., revising the DMP, consulting RDM support, arranging data agreements).
- **Store the completed form** with the updated DMP for future reference.

✓	<i>Discussion Points</i>	<i>Remarks</i>
<input type="checkbox"/>	1. Has the PhD candidate consulted you?	
<input type="checkbox"/>	2. Does the project involve personal, confidential, or IP-sensitive data; and are the associated risks recognized?	
<input type="checkbox"/>	3. Are the tools used TU/e approved and are they matching your project's data type, volume, and sensitivity?	
<input type="checkbox"/>	4. Is data received from or shared with external parties in a legally compliant and secure way?	
<input type="checkbox"/>	5. Is the data sufficiently documented and FAIR ready to enable understanding and future reuse?	
<input type="checkbox"/>	6. Is there a clear plan for archiving or retaining the research data in line with TU/e policy?	

Note: See appendix for more detailed information about each key discussion points.

Plan of action:

Appendix

As supervisors, your responsibility extends beyond guiding PhD candidates through their research trajectory—you are also accountable for the data they generate. In practice, *their data becomes your data*. This makes it essential to understand their plans for research data management across the entire data lifecycle, from initial planning to long-term archiving. Below are your responsibilities as PhD supervisors according to the [TU/e Research Data Management Framework Policy](#).

1. Support their PhDs in the preparation of a DMP for managing research outputs throughout their study or provide the DMP if already available.
2. Make sure the data management plan or protocol is being followed throughout the research trajectory.
3. Supervise and verify that PhDs take their role and responsibilities as specified in the policy.
4. Ensure that PhDs attend relevant training on research data management.

Below are six (6) key discussion points to address with your PhD candidates when reviewing their Data Management Plans (DMPs). These help ensure that their projects remain compliant with TU/e's RDM policy.

1. **Support and responsibility**

Has the PhD candidate consulted you?

Supervisor involvement is important not only for the scientific aspects of a PhD project, but also for research data management (RDM). At TU/e, all related RDM workflows are managed through the [Research Cockpit](#).

One of the first consultations should focus on developing the [Data Management Plan \(DMP\)](#), where decisions are made about how research data will be handled throughout the entire research lifecycle.

Supervisors are also encouraged to motivate their PhD candidates to build their RDM skills by pointing them to available training opportunities. Options include [DataBites](#) and departmental RDM trainings. For more detailed instructions and best practices, the [online RDM Handbook](#) is a valuable reference. If more in-depth support is needed, supervisors and PhD candidates are always welcome to contact their [departmental data stewards](#) for guidance.

Good to know: Once a DMP is submitted in the Research Cockpit, it is automatically assigned to the departmental data stewards. They assess compliance with the RDM policy, ensure alignment with best practices in FAIR, open, and responsible science, flag any potential privacy or ethical concerns, and connect you with other relevant research support services. This workflow ensures that data stewards are well-embedded in the process and consistently consulted. In many ways, *the DMP serves as your first ticket to research support!*

2. Data sensitivity and risks

🔊 **Does the project involve personal, confidential, or IP-sensitive data; and are the associated risks recognized?**

Good to know: What kind of data your candidates are handling?

- *Personal data* - any information that can directly or indirectly identify a living individual
- *Confidential or IP-sensitive data* - information that must be protected due to contractual, ethical, institutional, security requirements, or is or will be patented.

If the PhD candidate is working with human participants and handling personal data, it is mandatory to submit an application to the [TU/e Ethical Review Board](#) (ERB) and receive approval before the project can begin.

For all types of sensitive data, data stewards typically identify potential risks during the DMP review. Following this initial screening, the data stewards discuss these risks with the researchers and consult the appropriate support, such as [Privacy Operations](#), to obtain further guidance regarding [Privacy in Research](#). Together, they determine how to proceed with the research in a responsible manner, mitigate risks, implement suitable security measures, and protect the data throughout the entire research lifecycle.

If you are unsure whether your data is considered sensitive, consult the [Data Classification Guidelines](#). Establishing the correct classification is crucial because it indicates the protection measures and requirements your data must meet and guides you in selecting IT systems that provide the appropriate level of security. In practice, this means matching your data's classification level with the security level of available tools.

By having a clear understanding of the types of data your PhD candidates collect and process, we can also verify whether the tools and IT solutions they use comply with TU/e standards, which will be addressed in the next discussion points.

Good to know: If you are collecting personal data for research, you bear the responsibility of protecting each of the participants' privacy. One way to do this is to implement an appropriate anonymization or pseudonymization techniques which are available in [TU/e's De-identification Guidelines for Research Data](#), with [sample cases](#) available in the document created by Privacy Operations.

3. Storage and processing tools

🔊 **Are the tools used TU/e-approved, and are they matching with your project's data type, volume, and sensitivity?**

Throughout the “during research” phase, your PhD candidates may produce or handle varying amounts of data. Regardless of whether the data is sensitive, you must ensure that all data-related activities take place within TU/e–approved environments.

The TU/e Library and Information Services (LIS) offers a broad range of IT solutions that support every stage of the research data lifecycle. You can begin exploring these options through the [PAR Solution Searcher](#), where you can customize filters to identify the most suitable tools based on your specific needs and the type, volume, and sensitivity of the data involved.

Moreover, the Research Cockpit provides a comprehensive guidelines on [Research Data Solutions](#) available at TU/e. These are organized according to key stages of the data lifecycle, including:

- *Collection* (e.g. online surveys, IoT sensors, graphic or computer aided designs)
- *Processing* (e.g. quali/quantitative analysis, visualization, transcription, build models)
- *Collaboration* (e.g. working together on digital documents, codes/scripts)
- *Computing* (e.g. virtual workspace, high performance computing for AI)
- *Documentation* (e.g. literature manager, lab journals, plagiarism check)
- *Storage* (e.g. safe storage within TU/e or with external collaborators, encryption)

These resources are readily available to help you and your PhD candidates select the most appropriate and compliant solutions for your research workflows.

Good to know: If you are using a tool that is not listed in any TU/e resources, consider switching to one of the TU/e approved alternatives. However, if you have strong reasons to prefer a tool that is not yet approved, we encourage you to contact the data stewards to explore possible solutions. If the associated risks are low, we may be able to allow some flexibility. And if the tool appears valuable for the broader TU/e community, we can initiate the process of establishing a [data processing agreement](#), enabling its legal and compliant use at TU/e.

Moreover, with the rise of AI use in research, here are some available [guidelines for AI tools usage](#) for research and education.

4. Collaboration and data sharing

🔊 Is data received from or shared with external parties in a legally compliant and secure way (e.g. agreements)?

Sometimes, the research projects your PhD candidates work on are part of larger national or international consortia/partnerships involving universities or industry partners. These collaborations often require sharing or receiving data with external partners. In such cases, it is important to ensure that any data processed under TU/e's name has been lawfully acquired and is used appropriately.

You may need to check the lawful use of data if your project falls under any of the following situations:

- **You share or receive personal data, and/or IP-sensitive data** that you plan to collect, co-analyze, and co-publish with external collaborators.
- **You share or receive existing datasets** (containing personal and/or IP-sensitive data) for *secondary analysis*, especially when these datasets will be used independently for other research purposes.

TU/e provides a range of templates for different types of legal agreements. The TU/e data stewards can help you select the appropriate template and assist in preparing an initial draft using any of the available [data sharing agreement templates](#).

Identifying the need and the type of legal data sharing agreements is now integrated in the Research Cockpit workflow. When you indicate that your project involves sharing or receiving data from third parties, a Data Agreement form is generated to determine the conditions of your collaboration and data exchange and ultimately identify the most suitable type of agreement that works best for your project. The data stewards will be your first line of support in the preparation of the agreement drafts, which will then be taken over by the Privacy Operations team for technical review, before it will be signed by the managing directors of your respective departments. Don't worry, this will not delay or affect the pending ERB application, if ever you need one.

Good to know: If an agreement is already in place (e.g., main consortium agreement or a non-disclosure agreement), you are welcome to send it to the data stewards. They can assess whether the existing agreement is sufficient to cover lawful data sharing.

While we generally encourage the use of TU/e agreement templates, external collaborators sometimes prefer to use their own templates. In such cases, the [Privacy Operations team](#) must review the external template first to ensure it meets TU/e's legal and data protection requirements.

5. Documentation and publication readiness

🔊 **Is the data sufficiently documented and FAIR ready to enable understanding and future reuse?**

With the ongoing shift toward Open Science, the [FAIR Data principles](#) (**Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable**) are increasingly being adopted by research institutions and major funders as a foundation for good data management. As we progress further into the digital era, it is essential to ensure that research data aligns with these principles, so it remains future-proof and continues to create impact long after you or your PhD candidates have moved on.

To [make your data FAIR](#), encourage your PhD candidates to:

- Use consistent [file naming conventions](#) and [folder structures](#) so that data can be easily located and understood by others.
- Prepare clear [documentation and metadata](#) for each dataset, for example by including a well-structured [README file](#).
- Choose [preferred or open file formats](#) to maximize accessibility and long-term usability.
- Apply [version control](#) to track changes, prevent data loss, and support reproducibility.

Good to know: Need help making your research data FAIR before publication? TU/e Data Stewards run a [FAIR Data Clinic](#), where researchers can bring their “data patients” for hands-on support in improving findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability. Check the link to learn more and book a session.

In addition, as a technical university, TU/e researchers often produce not only traditional datasets but also substantial amounts of code, scripts, and software. Making these outputs FAIR is equally important—discover how to [make your software FAIR](#).

6. After the project

🔊 Is there a clear plan for publishing and archiving research data in line with TU/e policy?

Although it may seem early to consider how data will be published and archived after a project ends, planning ahead is essential. Defining PhD candidates' data packages from the outset reduces end-of-project stress and helps ensure all required components are in place. What's the difference though? *Publishing* data makes selected, well-documented datasets available for discovery and reuse, while *archiving* preserves data securely for the long term.

Regardless of whether data is published or archived, a complete data package is required to ensure the research can be understood, preserved, and, where appropriate, reused.

A [data package](#) must contain at least:

- Scientific documents (e.g., lab notes/diary, methodology & dataset-related documents, associated peer-reviewed articles, etc.)
- Administrative documents (e.g., DMPs, ERB approval, signed ICF, agreements, etc.)
- Code, script, computational models
- Data (raw and/or processed data)
- Research objects/materials (e.g., stimulus, questionnaires, experimental setup, etc.)
- Metadata form
- README file (including the appropriate license for sharing and reuse such as CC-BY 4.0 or MIT license for codes)

Publication: Research data can be published openly in one of TU/e's trusted repositories, such as [4TU.ResearchData](#) or [Zenodo](#), or in a suitable field-specific repository. These platforms support data discoverability, citation, and reuse in line with open science principles.

Archiving: TU/e has developed an internal repository, the [Research Archival Package Solution \(RAPS\)](#), which researchers can use to securely store data packages linked to published academic articles. RAPS supports long-term preservation, compliance with institutional requirements, and the safeguarding of scientific integrity

Good to know: Creating a data package for publication and archiving does not need to be treated as two separate processes. Instead, you can develop a single, complete, and comprehensive data package that includes all relevant materials—such as raw datasets—for internal archiving.

Once this full package is prepared, you can then select which datasets and documentation are appropriate and safe to make publicly available for reuse. This approach avoids duplication of effort and allows you to efficiently prepare data packages in one streamlined process.